

Teachers' Classroom Advisory Attitude in Relation to Satisfaction Among Students in Secondary Public Schools in Davao City

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Abstract. This study aimed to determine the relationship between teachers' classroom advisory attitude and students' satisfaction. In this study, the researcher selected 200 junior high school students in Cluster 3 public secondary schools in Davao City as the study's respondents. A stratified random sampling technique was utilized in the selection of the respondents. A non-experimental quantitative research design using a descriptive-correlational method was employed. The data collected were subjected to the following statistical tools: Mean, Pearson Moment Product Correlation, and multiple linear regression analysis. Findings revealed that teachers' classroom advisory attitude was described as extensive, while students' satisfaction in Cluster 3 public secondary schools in Davao City was moderately extensive. Further, correlation analysis demonstrated a significant relationship between teachers' classroom advisory attitude and students' satisfaction in Cluster 3 public secondary schools in Davao City. Evidently, regression analysis proved that teachers' classroom advisory attitude in terms of counseling services and handling disciplinary were significant predictors of students' satisfaction in Cluster 3 public secondary schools in Davao City. Hence, it was recommended that the Department of Education (DepEd) invest in ongoing training and development programs for teachers focusing on classroom management, interpersonal skills, and emotional intelligence.

KEY WORDS

1. Educational management
2. teachers' classroom advisory attitude
3. students' satisfaction

Date Received: October 05, 2024 — Date Reviewed: November 10, 2024 — Date Published: December 10, 2024

1. Introduction

Understanding how to improve student achievement, especially for struggling students, can be complex and daunting for advisory teachers. The tasks of advisory teachers in schools are essential in creating a climate conducive to educational, physically therapeutic, and effective communication and management based on caring and guidance services on the overall quality and effectiveness for the excellence of students and schools. In addition, the important attitude of classroom advisory teachers helps develop a sense of responsibility and diligence in providing help and assistance to students in terms of enrichment, development, prevention, and rehabilitation to enhance the knowledge, skills, and positive self-concept that may be necessary for producing civilized communities through counseling and guidance ser-

vices effectively, and trustworthy based on national educational philosophy. On a global scale, Mayo (2016) indicated a significant relationship between the classroom advisory attitude of teachers and student satisfaction. The study further showed that 33. Similarly, Grace and Teresa (2015) noted that classroom advisers' services in schools aim to assist the students in fulfilling their basic physiological needs, understanding themselves and developing associations with peers, balancing between permissiveness and controls in the school setting, realizing achievement, and providing. Ahmad and Zadhah (2018) note that guidance services help encourage students' academic, social, emotional, and personal development. In addition, Confidence (2019) asserted that guidance is an essential element in the discipline management of people in all societies. Even the most primitive societies grew out of the necessity of guiding an individual's behavior patterns in the group's interest. Accordingly, the main objective of the guidance is to help people understand themselves and deal with life experiences healthily by recognizing the factors that cause problems and looking for appropriate methods of resolving or avoiding the situations that may lead to unhealthy lifestyles. Meanwhile, Tamilenthirai and Mbewa (2015) noted that the increased wave of misconduct and its resultant effect showed that discipline had become a significant problem of educational management. It is observed that students resort to unconstitutional measures in channeling their grievances, and it is not unusual that schools have been blamed for the awkward and uncivilized behavior demonstrated by the students. In Kenya, the problem of indiscipline in secondary schools has escalated in the past few decades. Moreover, poor satisfaction with guidance services among students in essential education contexts remains an increasing problem among administrators and coun-

selors worldwide (Anyi, 2015). The report of Gallo (2017) showed that students who are less satisfied with the classroom advisory are not oriented with school programs and are more likely to fail in the class. The report further indicates that 66.67%. Taking things in the Philippine setting, it was found that students who are not satisfied with the schools and classroom advisers' services oftentimes have poor choices of courses in colleges (Pesigan, 2019). This is because students cannot cope with the complexity of the subjects when they enter the tertiary school level. After all, it does not fit their skills (Ogunmade, 2011). In addition to the problem stated above, the report of Cunningham (2013) also indicates that those students who show less interest in guidance services, which is indicated by their avoidance of participation in career choice programs, exhibit low performance in other subjects. This ugly trend may distract the students from being attentive during the teaching and learning process as they no longer have a positive attitude and interest in learning (Ovute Ovute, 2015). Although the researchers established the link between classroom advisory attitude and student satisfaction, a few issues remain unclear. First, previous studies focus on services implemented at the tertiary level. Second, the researcher has not yet found any study on the relationship between classroom advisory attitude and student satisfaction in secondary public schools in the Philippine context. Thus, this study addresses the gap in the current literature by placing a stronger emphasis on acquiring an understanding that would help students develop their interest in participating in classroom activities and school programs. Also, by exploring the factors that influence students' satisfaction, this study is expected to establish a pattern of acquiring skills and fill the gaps in the literature about the classroom advisory attitude of teachers.

2. Methodology

This section contains the research design, research respondents, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—The researcher employed a quantitative non-experimental design utilizing the correlational technique of research to gather data ideas, facts, and information related to the study, the researcher. Quantitative research, as described by Bhandari (2020), is a research strategy that focuses on quantifying the collection and analysis of data. Accordingly, quantifying is formed from a deductive approach where emphasis is placed on testing theory, shaped by empiricist and positivist philosophies. At the same time, non-experimental research lacks the manipulation of an independent variable. Rather than manipulating an independent variable, researchers conducting non-experimental research measure variables as they naturally occur in the real world. Meanwhile, according to Myers and Well (2013), descriptive-correlational research examines how the independent variable influences the dependent variable and establishes cause-and-effect relationships between variables. In this study, the researcher examined the relationship between teachers' classroom advisory attitude and student satisfaction. In this connection, the study explored which domains of the teachers' classroom advisory attitude significantly influence the students' satisfaction. In this study, the use of descriptive-correlational was appropriate because the researcher only focused on the behavioral aspect of the respondents, and the researcher was unable to experiment with a controlled set-up.

2.2. Research Respondents—The study's respondents were junior high school students in the Cluster 3 Secondary Schools in Davao City. In this study, the 200 respondents were selected through a stratified random sampling technique. Stratified random sampling is a method of sam-

pling that involves the division of a population into smaller sub-groups known as strata. According to Shi (2015), in stratified random sampling, or stratification, the strata are formed based on members' shared attributes or characteristics, such as income or educational attainment. Stratified random sampling is appropriate in this study because there is heterogeneity in a population that can be classified with ancillary information. In this study, certain inclusion criteria were implemented to determine the respondents. The primary consideration of this study is to select respondents who can provide information to achieve the purpose of this study. Hence, only those enrolled junior high school students in the Cluster 3 Secondary Schools in Davao City, those without back subjects and failed grades in the previous quarter, and those who voluntarily signed the ICF were given the survey questionnaires. Moreover, the study was delimited only to the nature of the problem based on the research questions, and, thus, it did not consider the gender and socio-economic status of the junior high school students.

2.3. Research Instrument—The study employed researcher-made questionnaires that fit the context of the respondents. The instrument was divided into two parts. The instrument's first part concerns the teachers' classroom advisory attitude. This questionnaire would measure counseling services, handling disciplinary cases, parent coordination, and guidance activities. The reliability of the new scale obtained a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.964, indicating high reliability and consistency among the items. In answering the questionnaire, the items were modified to suit the context of this answer and be answerable using the 5-Likert scale. As a guide in determining the extent of teachers'

classroom advisory attitude, the researcher used the range of means, descriptions, and interpretations presented below:

Range of Mean, Descriptive Level, and Interpretation

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The teachers' classroom advisory attitude is always observed.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The teachers' classroom advisory attitude is oftentimes observed.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The teachers' classroom advisory attitude is sometimes observed.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The teachers' classroom advisory attitude is rarely observed.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The teachers' classroom advisory attitude is never observed.

The second part of the instrument is about students' satisfaction, which was measured in terms of assurance, empathy, reliability, and responsiveness. The reliability of the new scale obtained a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.925, indicating high reliability and consistency among the items. In answering the questionnaire, the

items were modified to suit the context of this answer and be answerable using the 5-Likert scale. As a guide in determining the extent of student satisfaction, the researcher used the range of means, descriptions, and interpretations presented below:

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—The researcher underwent steps in conducting the study after validating the research questionnaire. Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher secured permission to conduct the study and the endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City. The endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City, was attached to the permission letters to be endorsed by the principals of the selected public schools in Cluster 3 Secondary Schools in Davao City. Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. After the

study was approved, the researcher distributed the research instrument to the respondents. The study was conducted last October 3-5, 2023. Upon distributing the questionnaires, the benefits of the survey were briefly discussed and explained to the identified respondents of the study. For the administration of the questionnaire, the questionnaire was distributed following health protocols such as wearing face masks and face shields and following social distancing. The study respondents were given enough testing time to finish the questionnaires. After this, the data collected were subjected to quantitative analysis. Collation and Statistical

Range of Mean, Descriptive Level, and Interpretation

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The students' satisfaction is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The students' satisfaction is oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The students' satisfaction is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The students' satisfaction is seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The students' satisfaction is never manifested.

Treatment of Data. After the questionnaire was retrieved, each respondent's scores were tallied to organize the data per indicator. After that, each score was subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis using SPSS.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following were the statistical tools utilized by the researcher in processing the gathered data: Mean. This was useful in characterizing the teachers' classroom advisory attitude and students' satisfaction in public secondary schools in Davao City. It was used to supply the answer for objectives 1 and 2. Pearson Product Moment Correlation. It was used in this study to assess the significant relationship between independent (teachers' classroom advisory attitude) and dependent (students' satisfaction) variables. It is a statistical measure of the strength of a linear relationship between paired data. In a sample, it is usually denoted by *r*. This was used to supply the answer for objective 3. Linear Regression was applied to evaluate the significance of the influence of the independent (teachers' classroom advisory attitude) variable on the dependent (students' satisfaction) variable. This was used to supply the answer for objective 4.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the data gathered. It is sequenced based on the study's objectives, as presented in the first chapter. Thus, it presents the extent of teachers' classroom advisory attitude and students' satisfaction in Cluster 3 Secondary Public Schools in Davao City and their significant relationship.

Teachers' Classroom Advisory Attitudes Table 1 summarizes teachers' classroom advisory attitude in Secondary Public Schools in Davao City. It shows that the overall mean of teachers' classroom advisory is 3.49, which is described as extensive. It means that the teachers' class-

room advisory attitude is oftentimes observed. More so, teachers' classroom advisory attitude in terms of handling disciplinary cases acquired the highest mean score of 3.65, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed. In contrast, teachers' classroom advisory atti-

tude in terms of guidance activity got the lowest mean score of 3.17, which was described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed by the teacher in Cluster 3 Secondary Public Schools in Davao City.

Table 1. Summary on Teachers' Classroom Advisory Attitudes in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Counselling Services	3.26	Moderately Extensive
Handling Disciplinary Cases	3.65	Extensive
Parents' Coordination	3.24	Moderately Extensive
Guidance Activity	3.17	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.49	Extensive

This implies that the approach and demeanor that teachers adopt when providing guidance, support, and mentorship to their students, particularly in a classroom or advisory setting, is oftentimes observed. The result agrees with the view of. This supports the findings of Grace and Teresa (2015) that teachers with a high level of classroom advisory attitude create a positive and inclusive learning environment. Students feel valued, respected, and supported, which can enhance their engagement and motivation to learn. This also supports the assertion of Ahmad and Zadha (2018) that high levels of advisory attitude often lead to stronger bonds between teachers and students. These relationships can facilitate better communication, trust, and collaboration, which, in turn, can lead to improved academic outcomes. Teachers with a positive advisory attitude provide emotional and psychological support to students.

Student Satisfaction in Cluster 3 in Public Secondary Schools

As shown in Table 2, is the summary of students' satisfaction in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City. As shown in the table, students' satisfaction obtained an overall mean score of 3.23 with a descriptive rating of moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes manifested by the students in cluster 3 public secondary schools. Adding more, results in Table 11 show that students' satisfaction in terms of assurance acquired the highest mean score of 3.56, described as extensive and interpreted as often manifested, while students' satisfaction in terms of responsiveness obtained the lowest mean score of 3.08, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes manifested by the students. The result indicates that the degree of contentment, happiness, and fulfillment students experience in relation to their

educational experiences, including their coursework, learning environment, and overall academic journey, is sometimes manifested. This supports the findings of Mandera (2013) that students with moderate levels of satisfaction may show varying levels of engagement with their studies. Some aspects of their education may be satisfying, while others may not meet

their expectations. Moderate student satisfaction suggests that there is room for enhancement in the educational experience. However, the result supports Gallo's (2017) idea that students' motivation can vary, with some being motivated by aspects they find satisfying and others experiencing reduced motivation due to areas of dissatisfaction.

Table 2. Summary of Students' Satisfaction in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Tangible	3.35	Moderately Extensive
Responsiveness	3.08	Moderately Extensive
Reliability	2.91	Moderately Extensive
Assurance	3.56	Extensive
Empathy	3.39	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.23	Moderately Extensive

Relationship Between Teachers' Classroom Advisory Attitudes and Students' Satisfaction in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City

The results of the analysis of the relationship between teachers' classroom advisory attitude and students' satisfaction in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City are presented. Bivariate correlation analysis using Pearson product-moment correlation was used to determine the relationship between the mentioned variables. Table 3 shows that teachers' classroom advisory attitude has a significant positive relationship with the students' satisfaction in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City with a p-value of .000 that is less

than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = 0.554, p < 0.05$). It means that as the extent of teachers' classroom advisory attitude changes, students' satisfaction also changes significantly. Adding more, results on the table shows that teachers' classroom advisory attitude in terms of counselling services; handling disciplinary cases; parents' coordination; and guidance activity have significant positive relationship with the students' satisfaction in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = 0.409, p < 0.05$), ($r = 0.533, p < 0.05$), ($r = 0.229, p < 0.05$), and ($r = 0.772, p < 0.05$), respectively.

Table 3. Relationship Between Teachers' Classroom Advisory Attitudes and Students' Satisfaction in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City

Variables	r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Counselling Services	0.409*	0.000	Significant	Reject H0
Handling Disciplinary Cases	0.533*	0.000	Significant	Reject H0
Parents' Coordination	0.229*	0.000	Significant	Reject H0
Guidance Activity	0.702*	0.000	Significant	Reject H0
Overall Teachers' Classroom Advisory Attitudes	0.556*	0.000	Significant	Reject H0

*Significant @ $p < 0.05$

This implies that teachers were able to provide personalized support and guidance to students. They recognize that each student has unique needs and may offer additional help when necessary. This individualized attention can enhance student satisfaction. The findings agree with Kruglanski et al.'s (2015) idea that a positive advisory attitude can inspire and motivate students. When teachers show enthusiasm for their subject matter and believe in their students' potential, it can encourage students to be more enthusiastic about learning. Positive teachers provide constructive feedback and support, which helps boost students' confidence. When students feel that their efforts are acknowledged and appreciated, they are more likely to feel satisfied and confident in their abilities. According to Shippen et al. (2005), positive teachers are good communicators. They listen to students, answer their questions, and provide clear explanations.

Influence of Teachers' Classroom Advisory Attitudes on the Students' Satisfaction in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City

The significance of the influence of teachers' classroom advisory attitude on the students' satisfaction in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools

in Davao City was analyzed using linear regression analysis. Table 4 shows that when teachers' classroom advisory attitude in terms of counseling services, handling disciplinary cases, parents' coordination, and guidance activity are considered predictors of student satisfaction, the model is significant, as evident in an F-value of 27.837 with a $p < 0.05$. Therefore, teachers' classroom advisory attitude predicts the students' satisfaction in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City. Meanwhile, the computed adjusted R² value of 0.351 indicates that teachers' classroom advisory attitude has contributed significantly to the variability of students' satisfaction by 35.10 from the total variability. Therefore, the difference of 64.90 was credited to other factors not covered in this study. In addition, the table shows that there are domains of teachers' classroom advisory attitude that significantly influence the students' satisfaction in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City. This table also indicates that teachers' classroom advisory attitudes in terms of counseling services and handling disciplinary cases are significant when the predictors are considered. This means that the extent of students' satisfaction increases by 0.161 and 0.295 for

each unit increase in teachers' classroom advisory attitude. Thus, this leads to rejecting the null hypothesis that none of the teachers' classroom advisory attitude domains significantly influence the students' satisfaction in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City.

Table 4. Influence of Teachers' Classroom Advisory Attitudes on the Students' Satisfaction in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City

Teachers' Classroom Advisory Attitudes	B	Beta	S.E.	p-value	Decision
Counselling Services	.161*	.231	.045	.000	Reject H0
Handling Disciplinary Cases	.295*	.408	.047	.000	Reject H0
Parents' Coordination	.085	.108	.049	.101	Accept H0
Guidance Activity	.007	.002	.034	.113	Accept H0
R² = 0.351		F-value = 27.837*		p-value = 0.000	

*Significant @ p<0.05

This affirmed that students' satisfaction is a function of teachers' classroom advisory attitude. The findings are in consonance with the study of Sprowel-Loftis (2013), which states that a positive advisory attitude helps build strong student-teacher relationships. When students feel they can trust and connect with their teachers, they are more likely to be satisfied with their learning experience. Lastly, the result corroborates with the proposition of Pincus

et al. (2020) that teachers with positive classroom advisory attitudes contribute to a more supportive and conducive learning environment. This, in turn, enhances students' satisfaction by fostering motivation, confidence, effective communication, and strong relationships. Students tend to be more engaged and less stressed, leading to greater overall satisfaction with their learning experience.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This part of the paper presents the researcher's conclusions and recommendations. The discussion was supported by the literature presented in the first chapters, and the conclusion is in accordance with statements of the problem presented in this study.

4.1. Findings—The primary objective of this study was to evaluate which domains of teachers' classroom advisory attitude significantly influence the students' satisfaction utilizing a non-experimental quantitative design using the descriptive-correlation technique. The

researcher selected the 200 junior high school students in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City as the respondents through a stratified random sampling method. The researcher used modified and enhanced adapted survey questionnaires that were pilot-tested in a

nearby school to ensure high reliability and internal consistency of the items in the instrument. Teachers' classroom advisory attitude in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City got an overall mean of 3.49 with an extensive descriptive rating. Also, teachers' classroom advisory attitude regarding counseling services, handling disciplinary cases, parents' coordination, and guidance activities obtained mean scores of 3.26, 3.65, 3.24, and 3.17, respectively. Students' satisfaction in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City has an overall mean of 3.32 with a moderately extensive descriptive rating. Also, students' satisfaction in terms of assurance, empathy, reliability, and responsiveness obtained mean scores of 3.35, 3.08, 2.91, 3.56, and 3.39, respectively. The result showed that teachers' classroom advisory attitude has a significant positive relationship with the students' satisfaction in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .556, p < 0.05$). Teachers' classroom advisory attitude in terms of counseling services and handling disciplinary cases significantly influenced the students' satisfaction in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City, as evidenced by the F-value of 27.837 and $p < 0.05$. The r^2 value of 0.351 indicated that teachers' classroom advisory attitude had contributed significantly to the variability of the students' satisfaction in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City by 35.10 from the total variability.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study several conclusions were generated: Teachers' classroom advisory attitude in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City was extensive. Meanwhile, teachers' classroom advisory attitude in terms of handling disciplinary cases obtained an extensive descriptive rating, while teachers' classroom advisory attitude in terms of counseling services, parents' coordination, and guidance activities got moderately extensive ratings. This implies that the approach

and demeanor that teachers adopt when providing guidance, support, and mentorship to their students, particularly in a classroom or advisory setting, is oftentimes observed. Students' satisfaction in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City were rated as moderately extensive. Students' satisfaction in terms of reliability got an extensive rating, while students' satisfaction in assurance, empathy, and responsiveness belonged to a moderately extensive rating. The result indicates that the degree of contentment, happiness, and fulfillment students experience concerning their educational experiences, including their coursework, learning environment, and overall academic journey, is sometimes manifested. The result showed that teachers' classroom advisory attitude has a significant positive relationship with the student's satisfaction in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City. This means that as the extent of teachers' classroom advisory attitude changes, students' satisfaction also significantly changes. This implies that teachers could provide personalized support and guidance to students. They recognize that each student has unique needs and may offer additional help when necessary. Teachers' classroom advisory attitude in terms of counseling services and handling disciplinary cases significantly influenced the students' satisfaction in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City. This affirms that students' satisfaction is a function of teachers' classroom advisory attitude in secondary public schools in Davao City.

4.3. Recommendations—Department of Education (DepEd) may invest in ongoing training and development programs for teachers focusing on classroom management, interpersonal skills, and emotional intelligence. These programs can help teachers develop more positive advisory attitudes. School heads may foster a supportive work environment where teachers are encouraged to collaborate and share best practices for improving teacher-student relation-

ships and satisfaction. They should also encourage teachers to participate in training programs and workshops that focus on building positive advisory attitudes and enhancing student satisfaction. Teachers may develop empathy and active listening skills to understand better and respond to students' needs and concerns. They should also tailor their approach to meet their students' individual needs. Recognize that each student is unique and may require different support and encouragement. Future researchers may research best practices for enhancing teacher advisory attitudes and student satisfaction and explore the impact of various teaching methods, interventions, and programs.

5. References

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